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COMMUNITY WITH A SHARED FUTURE FOR MANKIND** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252850>**ABSTRACT**

Human society has always been developing and changing since its birth. Every time the society develops to a certain stage, there will be new situations and new characteristics different from the past, and at the same time, new difficulties and new challenges will arise. Since the beginning of the 21st century, great changes have taken place in human society, the world economic system has been impacted, the global ecological and environmental problems have worsened, and the global governance plan has not been updated, putting human society in a period of great development, transformation, and adjustment, and facing unprecedented challenges. This article is dedicated to the analysis the historical background of the axiological concept of a community with a shared future for mankind.

Key words: community, mankind, five principles of peaceful coexistence, multi-polarization, dark mines.

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Докторант кафедры философии и логики НУУз**ИСТОРИЧЕСКАЯ ПРЕДПОСЫЛКА АКСЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КОНЦЕПЦИИ
ЕДИНОГО БУДУЩЕГО ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСТВА****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Человеческое общество всегда развивалось и менялось с момента своего рождения. Каждый раз, когда общество развивается до определенного этапа, возникают новые ситуации и новые характеристики, отличные от прошлого, и в то же время возникают новые трудности и новые вызовы. С начала XXI века в человеческом обществе произошли большие изменения, пострадала мировая экономическая система, глобальные экологические и экологические проблемы усугубились, а план глобального управления не был обновлен, что поставило человеческое общество в период Великого развития, преобразований и корректировок, а также столкновение с беспрецедентными проблемами. Данная статья посвящена анализу исторических предпосылок аксиологической концепции общности единой судьбы человечества.

Ключевые слова: сообщество, человечество, пять принципов мирного сосуществования, многополярность.

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O‘zMU “Falsafa va mantiq” kafedrası doktoranti**BIRLASHGAN INSONIYAT KELAJAGINING AKSIOLOGIK KONSEPSIYASINING
TARIXIY SHARTI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Insoniyat jamiyati paydo bo'lganidan beri doimo rivojlanib, o'zgarib bordi. Jamiyat har gal ma'lum bir bosqichga ko'tarilganda o'tmishdan farq qiladigan yangi holatlar, yangi xususiyatlar paydo bo'ladi, shu bilan birga yangi qiyinchiliklar, yangi chaqiriqlar paydo bo'ladi. 21-asr boshidan beri insoniyat jamiyatida katta o'zgarishlar yuz berdi, jahon xo'jalik tizimi zarar ko'rdi, global ekologik va ekologik muammolar og'irlashdi, global boshqaruv rejasi yangilanmadi, bu esa insoniyat jamiyatini buyuk davrga qo'ydi. rivojlanish, o'zgartirish va sozlash va misli ko'rilmagan muammolarga duch kelish. Ushbu maqola insoniyatning yagona taqdiri jamiyatining aksiologik kontsepsiyasining tarixiy asoslarini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: jamoa, insoniyat, tinch-totuv yashashning besh tamoyili, ko'p qutblilik.

INTRODUCTION.

The current international economic system is in the process of transformation and change. For more than 200 years, the international economic system has been dominated by the western capitalist countries, and the international market has been divided by the capitalist countries. After the two world wars, the old capitalist countries in the west were greatly injured, and the United States took the opportunity to make a great deal of money in the war, and rapidly rose to be the hegemon of the world. After the end of World War II, the United States as the leader of the developed countries by virtue of its absolute economic advantage, in the international economic system occupies a dominant position, and with other developed capitalist countries jointly constructed the international economic system political system, and jointly formulated a series of international relations regulations and norms. Obviously in the international market at that time, the United States as the leader of the capitalist countries have the absolute right to speak and dominate, this situation in the United States and the Soviet Union Cold War period was affected, but with the end of the Cold War, the Soviet Union as the leader of the socialist camp to the end of the failure of the tilt of the international situation, the United States in the international economic system in the hegemony of the position of the United States even more strengthened. With the expansion of the market economy, the advent of the new wave of scientific and technological revolutions, and the further advancement of globalization, the originally backward developing countries were rapidly transformed into new industrialized countries.

LITERATURE REVIEW.

According to Gao Dawei, from the Book of Rites, one of the five Confucian classics, to Sun Yat-sen (1866-1925) or Li Dazhao (1888-1927), the ideal of Kang Youwei (1858-1927) and the pursuit of 1927 are recurring themes in Chinese political tradition and philosophical discourse. The "community with a shared future for mankind" contains a long-term view of time and a broad view of space. China's "rejuvenation" is characterized by the interaction of rapid economic recovery and profound social and political changes. It is also a process of opening up to the outside world. China is not only a recipient of external thoughts and practices, but also a provider of ideas for opening up. Adhering to building a community with a shared future for mankind, China has chosen a geopolitical stance contrary to nationalist unilateralism. Although multilateralism has been questioned and weakened by the emerging forces of the United States, Beijing recognizes that organization is indispensable in a world where unprecedented multilateralism is interdependent, cooperative, dialogue and compromise. Global interdependence is naturally regarded as an inevitable reality, as a destiny choice, and we need to manage and organize it to advance construction not only at the national or macro-regional level, but also around the world as large as possible. In the "Orientalism" deconstructed by Edward Said (1935-2003), or in the "Westernism" reflecting it, the imaginary

other is always in a distant degradation, while the dualism of the East and the West is the appreciation and cultivation of meaningful interaction mechanism. The community with a shared future for mankind expresses a relationship between global interaction and mutual existence and the common destiny of mankind. Le gov (Jacques Le Goff) thinks, as a cultural entity of China, the biggest difference with Europe and the United States history, it is China once has a grand world view system (based on the "world" harmonious philosophy), it is neither the European and American empire system (based on power control philosophy), nor the European and American nation-state system (based on the "jungle" theory and evolution of competition philosophy).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The article uses the methods of comparative studies, analysis, synthesis, extrapolation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

With the rise of developing countries, parallel to the economic growth of developed countries in the West has entered a bottleneck, the pace of economic development has slowed down, and the world economic pattern has also seen a change of both sides of the fence, and the hegemony of the developed capitalist countries in the international economic sphere has been broken. In the 21st century, China, India, Brazil and other developing countries have been developing rapidly, occupying important seats in the international economic market, and providing a huge impetus for global economic development, and the trend of the world economic pattern towards multi-polarization has been set, and the hegemony of the Western capitalist countries has gone bankrupt. As a result of the new crown epidemic in the world, which accelerated the evolution of the great change that has not been seen in a hundred years, the new crown epidemic appeared in almost all the countries in the world, and the knock-on effect due to the epidemic hit the original international economic order and caused damage to the global economic system, and the economies of the vast majority of countries were in decline. By the impact of economic globalization, international trade, the international industrial chain, international financial activities have been hit hard, the stock market meltdown, economic stagnation and recession, foreign exchange shrinkage, rising financial risks and other situations so that the global economic pattern into the post epidemic era is also undergoing new changes, the world economic system is brewing to take place in a period of major changes, which affects the human society is unprecedented in the development of a major change of the big adjustment of the This is a period of unprecedented development, change and restructuring, and the challenges faced are unprecedented.

In addition, ecological and environmental problems have also become common issues that all countries in the world must deal with in a serious manner. As mankind in the process of social industrialization in the excessive pursuit of production capacity and efficiency and ignored the impact of industrialization on the ecological environment, until the environment has been overburdened, a series of "retaliation" against mankind has affected the survival and development of mankind, mankind will only move the focus of the industrial development and ecological environment to a balance on the ecological environment, ecological environment damage brought about by global threats, such as global climate change, the sharp decline in biodiversity, land desertification, water scarcity and other issues to a certain extent affect the economic development of countries. Global threats brought about by the destruction of the ecological environment, such as global climate change, the sharp decline in biodiversity, land desertification, water scarcity and other issues to a certain extent, affecting the way of economic development of all countries, people's way of life, there are many ecological problems, and not by a country or a few countries and regions will be able to solve the problem, the world is a universally linked as a whole, no matter how the sophists refute, can not change the link between the countries, therefore, the world's nations are not the same as the objective facts. The world is a universally linked whole, and no amount of sophistry can change the objective fact that countries are linked to each other. Therefore, all countries in the world should work together to find ways to effectively curb the side effects of ecological damage.

First of all, ecological and environmental problems can lead to the intensification of international conflicts. As people's understanding of the importance of the ecological environment deepens, they are able to clearly recognize the role of the ecological environment in social and economic development, as well as its importance in safeguarding national and even international security

interests. In areas where the environment is deteriorating and resources are in short supply, violent conflicts are frequent and expanding, and people will engage in vicious conflicts in order to seize more resources. Such disputes also occur between countries, and the wide coverage of the ecological environment sometimes causes friction between neighboring countries due to ecological problems, intensifying conflicts, which is not conducive to international peace and stability among regions. Secondly, people's protection of the ecological environment will also enhance international exchanges and cooperation. The impact of the ecological environment on human beings has become a consensus issue for all human beings, and many countries have carried out various forms of cooperation, such as signing environmental protection agreements and formulating international laws to promote the process of human environmental protection, and have continuously expanded the scope of international cooperation in the field of environmental protection, which covers land, water resources, endangered species, the ozone layer, greenhouse gas emissions, and other aspects of cooperation, and we should also pay attention to the active role of non-governmental organizations, such as environmental protection associations. At the same time, attention should also be paid to the positive role of non-governmental organizations, such as environmental protection associations, so that mankind can join forces to protect the ecological environment.

The many new problems and challenges that have arisen as a result of socio-economic development have also led to new dilemmas in global governance, and global governance programmes have not been effectively revised. Global governance goes hand in hand with globalization, and the global problems brought about by globalization need to be solved by the joint participation of international pluralistic subjects, such as countries, governmental organizations, non-governmental organizations and multinational corporations, through the joint formulation of international laws and regulations, the creation of an international mechanism, and the increase of moral constraints, in order to effectively solve the global problems. The outbreak of the financial crisis in 2008, which has fully highlighted the deficiencies of the original governance system, has been a major factor in the development of the global governance system. With the failure of the capitalist plutocrats' bailout, the western capitalist countries could no longer cope with the crisis by themselves, and the Group of Twenty (G20) came into being, with countries taking measures to negotiate and cooperate to cope with the crisis and stop its further deterioration in time. There is still an unavoidable contradiction in the current global governance system, i.e., as the complexity and severity of the global governance situation deepens, there is an urgent need for all countries in the world to fully cooperate with each other, especially the role of the big powers in it, but the big powers that dominate the global governance system are excessively concerned about their own national interests and security and are unwilling to assume the corresponding responsibility for governance, which worsens the political environment for global governance and impedes the construction and perfecting of the global governance system, and is detrimental to the international community. This deteriorates the political environment of global governance, hinders the construction and improvement of the global governance system, and is not conducive to the development of the international order and the international governance system in a just and reasonable direction. In fact, the most important subject of global governance is national governance, especially the participation of big countries that occupy an important economic and political position in the world. However, in reality, some western countries have been habitually transferring their conflicts to the outside world in the face of domestic problems, which has caused the deterioration of inter-country relations, and the construction of the global governance system is still a long-term, tortuous and complicated process, which is undoubtedly another great challenge to the development of human society.

The current international situation is presenting new characteristics and new forms different from the past, on the one hand, with the deepening of globalization, the degree of inter-country exchanges continue to diversify, frequent, from economic exchanges gradually expanded to political, cultural, information, technology and other exchanges, the world is becoming more and more of a community of destiny in which you are with me, and I am with you; on the other hand, the international conflict is also becoming more and more obvious, East and West. On the other hand, international conflicts are also becoming more and more obvious, the cultural differences between

the East and the West, the strategic game between the big powers, terrorism, local wars caused by regional radicalization, etc. have all added complexity to the evolution of the world pattern.

It can be seen that the complexity of the development of the world situation and the delicate relationship between countries have made it necessary for us to constantly explore new modes of getting along with each other. China has always advocated the democratization of international relations, adhered to the Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence, and has never aligned itself with any other country or claimed hegemony; it has always adhered to the concept of a community of human destiny, and has endeavoured to build a new type of international relations based on mutual respect and cooperation for a win-win situation, China has always upheld the concept of a community of human destiny, strived to build a new type of international relations based on mutual respect and win-win cooperation, and broken the political hegemony of the United States, Europe and other Western countries in the international arena, so that all countries in the world can have equal exchanges and live in peace with each other, and so that the world order will tend to stabilize. The concept of a community of human destiny was put forward in order to recognize the complexity of the international situation and to follow the laws of economic development; only cooperation is the way forward for the development of all countries, and only win-win cooperation is the result that the people of the world are looking forward to.

The current world peace and development is the theme of the times of the general trend has not changed, the deepening of economic globalization, the development of more comprehensive social information, multicultural exchanges, all the phenomena of globalization reflects the theme of peace and development of the world's people's common expectations and aspirations. Just as there are always shadows under the sunshine and challenges in the midst of opportunities, there are still many uncertainties and problems in human society that are destroying the peaceful environment for the survival of mankind. It will take a long time to fulfill the destiny of peace and development for mankind. The world is facing many common challenges, such as the lack of momentum in world economic growth, the growing polarization between the rich and the poor, the ups and downs of regional hotspot issues, and the persistent spread of non-traditional security threats such as terrorism, cybersecurity, major infectious diseases, and climate change. Peace and development are in a dialectical and unified relationship, and only in a peaceful environment can we realize full development, and only in continuous development can we understand the importance of peace. Therefore, we should correctly recognize and treat the relationship between peace and development, maintain peace in the right way and promote development in a sustainable manner. Peace is the basis and condition for the social development of human existence. Human beings have experienced two world wars, which have posed a great threat to the lives of people all over the world. How many people have lost their lives in the wars, how many families have been torn apart, and how many human civilizations have been destroyed and have since been annihilated in the dust of history. The issue of world peace has become an unavoidable important issue for the development of all countries after the Second World War. World peace cannot be realized only by the advocacy of a few countries, but requires the joint efforts of all mankind and the cooperation of the whole world to deal with all kinds of potential "dark mines" and sudden challenges. However, due to the lack of consensus, some countries are still unable to take a holistic and long-term approach, giving too much consideration to their own national interests and paying too much attention to their current interests, thus loosening the world security structure.

In addition to inter-State games, the security threats of interregional terrorism and nationalism are becoming more and more prominent. Shocked the world when the "9-11" incident, terrorism to the United States to retaliate, to the world demonstration, this extremely unstable factor has become a major threat to world peace, attempting to undermine the national security of all countries, endangering the safety of people's lives, our country has also suffered from the invasion of terrorism, the independence of the Xinjiang, Tibetan independence and other terrorist forces in our country to the provinces and cities to infiltrate, in an attempt to undermine the safe and harmonious social environment in our country, riot attacks also occur frequently in Europe. Our country has also suffered from the onslaught of terrorism, with terrorist forces such as the independence of Xinjiang and

Tibetan independence infiltrating our provinces and cities in an attempt to undermine the safe and harmonious social environment in our country. From this we can see that terrorism has become a security factor that the whole world must face in the 21st century. In addition, the threat of weapons of mass destruction has also become an insecurity factor for world peace. The emergence of the North Korean nuclear issue and the Iranian nuclear issue has drawn attention to the dangers of nuclear threats, and nuclear weapons have become an important bargaining chip for some countries in the international community, making the Western powers worry about the threat to international security posed by the misuse of nuclear weapons. In addition, large-scale infectious diseases are also a threat to human life, from smallpox and the Black Death to Ebola and the SARS virus to the new coronavirus, the proliferation of each infectious disease has jeopardized the health and safety of human beings, and at the same time stimulated a lot of instability and social unrest, which has caused huge losses of life and property. The emergence of various destabilizing factors is, to a certain extent, due to the fact that some countries are still under the influence of traditional political thinking, with poor international communication and unsound mechanisms, resulting in security difficulties.

Development provides new momentum and opportunities for peace and stability. With the deepening of economic globalization, the degree of economic interaction, political trust and cultural integration among countries has deepened, demonstrating that the countries of the world have become a community of destiny in which you are one with me and I am one with you. Although there were still anti-globalization voices in some countries, it had been proved that the general trend of globalization had become a certainty. The core content of globalization belongs to economic globalization, and the trend of globalization in the economic field is what people started to carry out the most. Economic globalization has accelerated the global circulation of capital, trade, and labor, and promoted the level of growth of the global economy, and at the same time led to the trend of globalization in various fields, and facilitated the exchanges and development of human civilization. However, economic globalization and globalization are not the same, economic globalization is only one aspect of globalization, in fact, in ancient times, there have been the beginnings of globalization, China's ancient "Silk Road" increased the economic and cultural and technological exchanges between the people of the Asian and European continents, and promoted the development and prosperity of the inter-regional development, but due to the limitations of the transportation technology at that time, the cycle of globalization was slower. However, due to the limitations of transportation technology at that time, the cycle of globalization was slow. With the capitalist industrial revolution, the booming development of technology accelerated the process of globalization, realizing the great prosperity of global trade, the movement of people, and the prosperity in the economic field at a speed that people can see and touch, so that the first thing people think of when they mention globalization is the globalization of the economy. After the baptism of globalization, the ties between the countries of the world have become increasingly close, which is reflected in the economic, political and cultural exchanges and interactions, and at the same time, the threats and challenges faced by all countries have become more and more common features. Of course, these common threats need countries to cooperate and coordinate with each other in order to overcome them, so it can be reflected that "mankind is increasingly becoming a community of destiny with common interests, facing common challenges, bearing common responsibilities and possessing common values." [1,6]

The megatrend of globalization is an objective requirement for development, reflecting the fact that openness and progress are important factors that cannot be ignored in the development of the global economy, as well as an important catalyst for the exchange and development of human civilization. Nowadays, globalization is a diversified and parallel globalization, which is interwoven with industrialization, informationization and other advanced elements. The rapid development of our country's socialist modernization is also inevitably inseparable from the tide of globalization that our country has ridden and seized the opportunities of globalization. Although the phenomenon of anti-globalization has arisen due to the rise of protectionism, tariffism, regionalism and other forces as a result of a variety of factors, these various "isms" and "alliances" against the tide of history are only the dying struggles of narrow-minded historians. But these various "isms" and "alliances" against

the trend of history are inevitably only the death struggle of narrow-minded historians. China should grasp the good opportunities and avoid the risks in the trend of globalization, scientifically grasp the two major patterns of domestic and international affairs, continuously promote the process of socialist modernization in China, and show its due great power demeanor and great power responsibility in the international community, so as to continuously promote the historical process of globalization.

Through continuous development and interpretation, this idea has basically formed four core concepts, namely, security, prosperity, openness and greenness. These are the basic values for human survival in the new era, and are the central tenets of a new form of life for humankind and a new operating law for history.

In his speech at the United Nations on September 28, 2015 Xi Jinping elaborated on the connotation of the community of human destiny, "We should establish a partnership of equal treatment, mutual consultation and mutual understanding, create a security pattern of fairness and justice, and common construction and sharing, seek open and innovative development prospects that are inclusive and mutually beneficial, promote exchanges of civilizations that are harmonious and different, and construct an ecological system that respects nature, green development of the ecological system." [2] This reference mainly centers on politics, economy, culture, and ecology, and the basic kernel of the community of human destiny has been initially established. In October 2017, in the report of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China (CPC), it was stated that "building a world of lasting peace, universal security, common prosperity, openness and inclusiveness, cleanliness and beauty" [3, 59]

The connotation of this idea has become clearer and simplified, with the concepts of peace, prosperity, openness, and greenness basically presented. On December 1, 2017, in the World Conference on Political Parties, General Secretary Xi Jinping pointed out the need to strive to build a world that is free from fear and universally secure, free from poverty and jointly prosperous, free from closure and open and inclusive, and where mountains and rivers are clear and beautiful, and where mountains and rivers are clean and beautiful. Once again, the core concepts of security, openness, prosperity and greenness were highlighted.

Its primary core concept is security. Security is the basic bottom line for the survival and development of humankind, and it is the fundamental concept of this philosophy, especially now that the challenges of globalization are becoming more and more pronounced. While the community of human destiny aims to build "four worlds", the first step is to build a "safe" world, which is a prerequisite for the realization of the other "worlds". Without a peaceful and tranquil environment for the development of human society, all other economic prosperity, cultural prosperity and environmental beautification would be illusory. Human society has always had a vision of "security", "peace", "stability" and so on, because war and human society have always been intertwined. Although peace has become the mainstream of the world, local wars still cannot be completely avoided, and the threat of war to mankind has not completely disappeared, and even faces more complex security threats. For example, the threat of nuclear weapons, the threat of network security, the threat of viruses, the threat of climate, and so on, are by no means less harmful to mankind than a war. Therefore, in the context of globalization, it is all the more important to advocate a new concept of security and a new concept of peace, to eliminate all kinds of apparent and potential security risks, so that everyone can enjoy a peaceful and tranquil living environment.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS.

Shared prosperity is the material guarantee for moving towards a community of destiny. According to Marx's materialist conception of history, the economic base is the ultimate force that determines historical development, and the material improvement of life and living conditions for all humankind is the solid cornerstone of the forging of such a community. In today's world, although the level of material and technological development has improved by leaps and bounds, the problem of imbalance in global development is still prevalent, and poverty and hunger are still the primary problems in some places. By adhering to the concept of common prosperity, every part of the world can be free from poverty and hunger, injury, disease and embarrassment, and a new economic globalization that is inclusive and shared, rather than the old globalization that is patronizing and self-

serving, can be used to achieve the common development of the human community and to jointly promote the common prosperity and progress of all countries in the world.

CONCLUSION

Openness and inclusiveness are at the core of building a community of human destiny. Since we can form a "community", how can we live together in harmony, resolve differences, melt barriers and reach a consensus, so as to ultimately form a solid community? Chinese culture has always emphasized tolerance: "All things grow together without harming each other, and the Way runs in parallel without contradicting each other." It advocates harmony and difference, and acceptance, so as to bring a diversified landscape and multi-dimensional perspectives to human civilization. As global society develops today, its plurality and richness continue to emerge, which objectively enhances the possibility of exchanges and mutual understanding among different peoples, cultures and beliefs. Therefore, we should not look at civilizations different from our own with a "heretical" mindset or an "other" perspective, but rather with an open and tolerant mindset to integrate different civilizations, so that different civilizations can move towards continuous improvement through mutual learning. It can be seen that the community of destiny is a kind of "spiritual community" that is formed through deep cultural contact and frequent interaction among civilizations, which gives human beings common ideals and values, enables people to reach a consensus to the greatest extent possible in the midst of the complexity of things, and forms the synergy of development.

A clear, clean and beautiful landscape is a guarantee for building a community of human destiny. The natural environment is the common living space of human beings, and this limited physical space is irreplaceable, caring for the common home, guarding the common blue sky has become the external guarantee of the common destiny of mankind. Industrial civilization has developed to the present stage, people's ecological concepts and environmental awareness have been greatly enhanced, people are increasingly aware of the importance of clean air, high-quality water, clean green space, lush vegetation on human daily life. An excellent living environment also requires people's common maintenance and joint efforts, so the community of destiny can also be said to be an ecological community, a green community, and human beings can only maintain the dignity and order of human common life in a mountainous, clean and beautiful environment.

The four concepts of security, prosperity, openness and greenness together hold the cultural connotation of the community of human destiny and reveal a new path and direction for the development of human civilization. This concept, which China has proposed and taken the lead in putting into practice, has opened up a new form of civilization in the global community that is different from the Western civilization that has led the world for many years. The community of human destiny has glued together the destiny of mankind, which has been increasingly divided in human society, with global values constantly colliding and the world environment gradually deteriorating, and opened up a brand new path of survival for the future of mankind. Whether for individuals or for the rules of historical operation, the life of the community is the basic way of survival for individual and all human beings, as well as the path for future development. This cultural philosophy of community is not so much a transcendence of Western modernity and industrial civilization as a return to the essential culture of mankind.

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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

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ЎШБУ ЖУРНАЛ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ, ФАН ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВАЗИРЛИГИ ТОМОНИДАН МОЛИЯЛАШТИРИЛГАН ИЛ-4821891548 “ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАҲДИД ВА ДАЪВАТЛАР ШАРОИТИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ВА БЕЛАРУСЬ ЁШЛАРИ ОНГИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-МАДАНИЙ ВА АКСИОЛОГИК АСОСЛАРИ” НОМЛИ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬ ЛОЙИҲА ДОИРАСИДА НАШРГА ТАЙЁРЛАНГАН.

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ДАННЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ПОДГОТОВЛЕН К ИЗДАНИЮ В РАМКАХ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОГО НАУЧНОГО ПРОЕКТА ИЛ-4821891548 “СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ И АКСИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СОЗНАНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И БЕЛАРУСИ В УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УГРОЗ И ВЫЗОВОВ”

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